

COVERAGE OF THE IMAGE OF A WOMAN IN UZBEK FICTION

Abdullayeva Umida Abdumutal qizi

Phd student, National University of Uzbekistan

umidaabdullayeva0306@icloud.com

Annotation. This article mainly talks about the illumination of the female image in Uzbek fiction. In Uzbek literature, beautiful works are written that reflect the inner and outer beauty of the female breed, chastity and wisdom, intelligence, charm. In this article, the peculiarities of the female characters in Pirimkul Kadyrov's "Starry nights" are covered from the point of view of literary studies and Linguistics. The novel is dedicated to the life path of the ruler and poet Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, and deals mainly with the women who played an important role in Babur's life, their inner world, and their dreams.

Keywords. The image of a woman, the place of a woman in the family, the place of a woman in society, Qutlug Nigar Khanum, Khonzodabegim, linguistic analysis, issues of literary studies.

Introduction

The work "Starry Nights", which belongs to the famous Uzbek writer Pirimkul Kadyrov, is a historical novel written to the life of the great poet and prodigy leader Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur. The work highlights the events of Babur from his childhood to his death, the challenges he has experienced, the battle-it is the games of intensity, cunning, fidelity, justice and destiny. This work was considered the fruit of the ten years of work of Pirimkul Kadyrov and was written between 1969 and 1978. The writer's use of rare biographical works, such as the "Boburnoma" and the "Humoyunnoma", in the process of writing the work, also made the novel extremely lively and attractive. The work has been translated into various languages of the world including Russian, Bengali, Kyrgyz, Kazakh, Turkmen, Karakalpak, Turkish, Japanese. In addition, the work has been translated into English twice, with the first

translation done in 2019 by the staff of Samarkand State University of foreign languages and published in Samarkand. The second translation was done by the well-known English translator Karol Ermakova in 2023, and this translation was published at the Nouveau Monde publishing house.

Uzbek fiction cannot be imagined without a female image. And the work "Starry Nights", which is studied as a source of research, is not about the image of an ordinary Uzbek woman, but about the ladies of the House of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, a continuation of the Great Timurid dynasty. It is no secret that the path of fate that Babur went through as King and commander was not simple and easy, of course. It was thanks to this that the fate of the women around Babur, his mother, sister, wives, also went hard. Uzbek woman, whether she is an ordinary woman of an ordinary family, or a representative of a great dynasty, supports a man next to her in difficult times, raises difficulties to overcome together, gives hope. The female characters Qutlug Nigor Khanum, Khonzodabegim, Oisha begim, Fatima Sultan, Mohim begim appear in the work.

Lady Qutlug Nigor is the daughter of Yunus Khan of the Mongol dynasty, wife of Umarshaykh Mirzo, mother of Babur Mirza. In the process of reading the work, we will get to know her more closely and witness how wise, kind, humane and sincere she is. This image is especially remembered for its wisdom, wise thoughts even in matters of politics. Let us further illuminate this with the following examples from the work. Upon the death of Umarshaykh Mirzo, his 12-year-old son Babur Mirzo comes to the throne. Wanting to take advantage of Babur's young age, the Becks encourage him to march to Samarkand in an effort to gain even more wealth. Qutlug Nigor Khanum, Babur's mother, opposes this, and proceeds to dissuade Kasimbek, one of Babur's trusted bachelors, from the faction. We will find out why she opposed this in the following sentences:

- "The time will come when your dream about Samarqand will become true Now everybody wants to live in peace. You have such a wise vizier as Kasimbek. Such a talented man as the architect, who has built the Osh dwelling-place, serves you. Your mother begs you: put off Samarqand uneasiness for a few years. Hanzoda is right:

you should better start working at developing the valley, build wonderful palaces and madrasah in Andijan, Margilan and Osh!”⁹⁵

From the passage above, we can understand that there are several reasons why our lady of good will oppose the Samarkand March. The first of these is, of course, the unwillingness of the young to enter the whirlwind of war. On the other hand, thinking of her people as the Queen of the Kingdom, she also resists the fact that bloody wars drain the common people, knowing that the people are already fed up with wars. Kasimbek, who is one of Babur's trusted Becks, however, claims that the other Becks are in favor of new campaigns, saying that now Babur's authority is somewhat incapable of making great constructions, and insists that it is necessary to improve the material situation with new spoils by fighting again. At the same time, Qutlug Nigor Khanum insists on her opinion, citing very reasonable grounds in such a conflict situation that is happening with Mr. Kasimbek.

-“Mister Kasymbek, amir Timur and Mirza Ulugbek were not the only ones to undertake great constructions. Mir Alisher built the famous trinity in Heart: Ikhlosiya, Khalosiya and Unsiya. And the power of mirza Babur is not lower than the power of Mir Alisher.”⁹⁶

It is admirable that Qutlug Nigor Khanum is able to stand firm on sensitive issues, defend her point of view with appropriate reasoning. Lady Queen's daughter Honzodabegim, Babur's sister, was also not inferior to her mother in intelligence.

Khonzodabegim was distinguished from other temurian Princesses of the time by her wisdom, brilliance. Khonzodabegim was not only a beautiful princess, but also an adviser to her brother on political issues, being together with him at times when her brother was extremely sad. These warm situations are very beautifully illuminated in the work.

- “My amirzoda, isn't it better to build new palaces and medreses in Andijan instead of a Samarqand campaign which would take much expense? If Andijan will become equal to Samarqand with its beauty and luster, you will glorify your name

⁹⁵ P. Qodirov. Starry nights. Babur. Translation by I.M. Tukhtasinov, U.R. Yoldoshev, A.A. Khamidov. Samarkand-2019. p-75

⁹⁶ P. Qodirov. Starry nights. Babur. Translation by I.M. Tukhtasinov, U.R. Yoldoshev, A.A. Khamidov. Samarkand-2019. p-77

*like Mirza Ulugbek, - that is the cherished wish of your sister, and I wish god let you accomplish it!"*⁹⁷

We can see how sincere and passionate Khonzodabegim is. The main reason for her opposition to the new march is not only the fact that she is envious of his brother's soul, but also her deep sympathy for her people is vividly manifested. In the course of the work, the situations for the younger brother of Khonzodabegim, who gave up her interests, are very common. To save her brother from the siege, she is forced to marry a man older than his father, Babur's archenemy Shayboniy Khan. And when Babur is expelled from his land, Khonzodabegim also goes through any difficulties together, standing shoulder to shoulder with his brother.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in the image of these two women we can see the place taken by women in the life of the founder of the great Baburian dynasty, Babur.

⁹⁷ P. Qodirov. *Starry nights. Babur*. Translation by I.M. Tukhtasinov, U.R. Yoldoshev, A.A. Khamidov. Samarkand-2019. p-74